

TNF- α AND HSP70 AS MARKERS OF INFLAMMATION AND CELLULAR STRESS IN A HYDRONEPHROSIS MODEL: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Hydronephrosis represents a serious medical and social problem, as its progression leads to irreversible changes in renal tissue structure and the development of chronic kidney failure. In recent years, an increase in the number of patients with obstructive uropathies has been observed, which directly contributes to the rising incidence of hydronephrosis. The reasons for this growth include the prevalence of urolithiasis, age-related changes in the urinary system, the increasing occurrence of oncological diseases, and the detection of congenital anomalies in children [Sidorov, 2022].

Despite advances in ultrasound, computed tomography, and radionuclide diagnostics, the problem of early detection remains relevant, as clinical symptoms are often nonspecific or absent. This leads to diagnosis at later stages, when functional impairments of the kidneys become irreversible [Kuznetsova, 2023].

Moreover, hydronephrosis requires a multidisciplinary treatment approach involving urologists, nephrologists, and radiologists. The development of optimal algorithms for monitoring and treating patients with various forms of the condition is an important task in modern urology. The significance of this topic is further reinforced by the need to prevent disability, improve prognosis, and enhance the effectiveness of medical care. All of this underscores the high relevance of studying hydronephrosis in contemporary clinical practice.

Objective. To investigate the inflammatory and cellular stress markers TNF- α and HSP70 in a hydronephrosis model.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted according to GLP standards on 30 rats (180–240 g), divided into intact, sham-operated, and experimental groups (n=10). After a one-week acclimatization period, blood (3–4 ml) and kidney tissue samples were collected on days 1, 5, and 14 under ether anesthesia. In the sham group, a similar procedure was performed without ureter ligation. Serum obtained after centrifugation (3000 rpm, 8 min) was analyzed for TNF- α using ELISA with the “Scitek EMLR-112” kit. Kidney samples were prepared for Western Blot analysis: homogenization, centrifugation (12,000 rpm, 30 min, 4 °C), electrophoresis, transfer to PVDF membranes, incubation with primary and secondary antibodies, and visualization using ECL. Statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA (p=0.05) in GraphPad Prism 8.0.

Results and Discussion. In the control group, the TNF- α level remained stable (77.52 ± 8.23 pg/ml). In the sham-operated group, a moderate increase was observed—from 87.41 ± 9.86 to 98.16 ± 12.90 pg/ml by day 14—which reflects a nonspecific inflammatory response. In the experimental group, the TNF- α concentration was significantly higher and progressively increased ($148.70 \pm$

14.55 → 176.66 ± 23.78 pg/ml), confirming the development of pronounced inflammation in hydronephrosis.

To assess cellular stress, HSP70 expression was evaluated using Western blot analysis. In animals with ureteral obstruction, an increase in HSP70 was observed as early as day 1, representing an early response to tissue injury and impaired urodynamics, whereas no significant changes were detected in the control, sham, or Op Healthy groups. By day 7, HSP70 expression in the pathological group markedly decreased, indicating exhaustion of stress-adaptive mechanisms and progressive tissue damage. In the sham group, only a minor nonspecific elevation was noted. By day 14, the HSP70 level increased slightly but remained lower than in the control group, confirming a persistent insufficiency of the cellular stress response.

Conclusions:

1. Unilateral obstruction of the urinary tract induces progressive inflammation, as evidenced by a significant increase in TNF- α and an early induction of HSP70, which reflects the rapid activation of the cellular stress response in renal tissue.

2. The decrease in HSP70 expression alongside the continued rise in TNF- α indicates exhaustion of adaptive mechanisms and worsening parenchymal damage, allowing both markers to be considered informative indicators of the severity and progression of hydronephrosis.

References:

1. Гусев Н.Н., Ким И.П. Врожденные аномалии мочевыводящих путей как причина гидронефроза у детей // Педиатрическая хирургия. – 2019. – №3. – С. 15–20.
2. Сидоров А.В. Обструктивные уропатии у взрослых: структура, причины и методы лечения // Российский медицинский журнал. – 2022. – №9. – С. 56–62.
3. Кузнецова М.А. Значение лучевых методов исследования в ранней диагностике гидронефроза // Медицинская визуализация. – 2023. – №1. – С. 40–47.
4. Шаповалов А.В. Минимально инвазивные методы лечения гидронефроза: эффективность и риски // Клиническая урология. – 2020. – №6. – С. 72–78.